

Study of Vowels in English and Uzbek Languages

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Annotation:

Uzbeks have many difficulties when it comes to learning the vowels in English and Uzbek languages. The difficulty associated with pronunciation is closely related to the lack of contact and interaction with native speakers, differences in the phonological systems of English and Uzbek, and the lack of knowledge about pronunciation in schools and universities.

Keywords: Accommodation, ellision, deletion, reduction, monophthong, diphthong, triphthong, voice, tone, sound composition, accent, vowels.

Vowels are divided into monophthongs and diphthongs based on the standards of literary English pronunciation. A monophthong is a pure, unchanging, simple composition consisting of one sound, while diphthongs consist of a combination of two vowel sounds. The pronounced vowel in a diphthong is called a *nucleus*, and the weak component vowel is called a *glide*. In the formal English alphabet, six vowels are defined, but in pronunciation, 12 monophthongs and 8 diphthongs are distinguished. Based on these diphthongs and monophthongs, differences in the pronunciation of dialects are built, i.e., the characteristics of the accent. In live speech, vowel sounds undergo certain changes, these changes depend on the phonetic environment in which the vowel sound occurs and the speaker's articulatory capabilities. That is, a certain vowel changes depending on what sounds it belongs to, and changes its characteristics under the influence of consonants. The main types of changes include:

1. Accommodation – change under the influence of a consonant;
2. Ellision – loss, shortening of a sound element in speech. In the vowel system, ellipsis occurs in diphthongs;
3. Deletion – the shortening and complete disappearance of the vowel sound occurs as a result of fast speaking;

4. Reduction – in this case, the vowel sound is significantly shortened, but does not disappear completely.

While diphthongs and monophthongs form the basis of the pronunciation difference of dialects, the above-mentioned clauses are the main types of change that occur in the speech manifestation of the vowel sound. For example, in the American dialect of English, the sound combination oo is reduced and pronounced as u, while in the British dialect, we observe that the sound of u expands and approaches the sound of o.

The vowel sound system and its features are summarized in phonetics under the term vocalism. An example was given above that language dialects differ from each other according to the indicators of vocalism. Phoneticians list the following as the main elements of vocalism:

1. Voice;
2. Tone;
3. Sound composition;
4. Monophthong, diphthong and triphthong;
5. Accent;
6. Vowels¹.

As you can see, vocalism in language is not limited to vowels. Vowels occupy an important, core part of this paradigm. Tone, voice, and accent are located on the periphery of the field. Vowels come first because they can influence the tone and rhythm of pronunciation. There are different pronunciation options for unliking in English. If we look at the example of the vowel a, the a in the first syllable of the word accommodation is an open, active vowel pronounced as /æ/, and in the second syllable, the same sound is pronounced as /ə/ and becomes a closed, inactive vowel. English phonetics divides the sounds a, o, u, i, and e as basic vowels. Depending on the place of occurrence of the sound, its place of formation in the human speech apparatus differs. Accordingly, vowels are divided into open, closed and semi-closed types. Vowels are harmonious or disharmonious depending on their environment. For example, in the word "book" vowel sounds are combined with consonants, resulting in the sound "u". However, in the words "first" and "bit", i does not merge with the consonants in the composition and is distinguished. Such features are manifested differently in regional dialects. The study of dialectal vocalism is relevant in determining the range of phonetic possibilities of the language, introducing language learners to different dialects, and developing the criteria for simultaneous translation of dialectal speech.

The dialect indicates that language is a living, ever-changing social phenomenon. Linguists around the world consider it a priority to standardize literary language norms and bring them as close as possible to live speech. It is based on the most common dialect. In particular, the norms of the literary Uzbek language are based on the Qarluq dialect, the dialect of the Fergana Valley. The reason for this is that the Karaluq dialect has become the standard of speech of the inhabitants of the densely populated, trade-developed cities. Literary language is also modeled on this widespread dialect. Dialects differ from each other in terms of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammatical structure. Dialects of English with a long colonial history differ on different continents. In general, English as a means of international communication is characterized by a high frequency of changes and updates. English dialects are classified geographically. In addition to standard English, three main dialectal areas are distinguished:

¹ Rogers, H. The sounds of language: An introduction to phonetics. Edinburgh: Pearson Education Limited, 2000; Car F. English phonetics and phonology. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers Ltd, 1999.

1. British Isles;
2. America;
3. Australasia.

Language learners often confuse dialect with accent. Accent means a phonetic distinction from a literary language as a specific pronunciation system of a region, a certain group. Dialect differs from literary language not only in pronunciation, but also in grammatical structure and lexical content. Dialects in English-speaking countries have regional characteristics. English dialectologists found that there are more than 50 types of dialects in the British Isles².

There are eight diphthongs in modern English literature: [ɪ], [aɪ], [ɔɪ], [aʊ], [ɪə], [eə], [əʊ], [ʊə]. There are also diphthongoids [i:], [u:], which are closer to a diphthong than a simple vowel. In addition, triphthongs [aʊə], [aɪə], [əʊə], [eɪə], [ɔɪə] are distinguished in English. The longest sound of diphthongs and triphthongs is called its nucleus. Dialects and dialects can be distinguished according to which sound is pronounced long in the compound vowel. The short sound in the composition is called glide. In some regions, the short element is pronounced longer or indistinctly. In triphthongs, the first sound of the composition is stressed, its pronunciation is clearly known due to the lengthening of the syllable. Below are some words that contain triphthongs:

dire	inspire
employer	layer
fire	lire
hour	lower
mower	loyal
player	power

In general, the accent feature of English vocalism differs from Germanic languages in one respect. Unstressed vowels are naturally pronounced shorter than stressed vowels. This can be proved by the example of diphthong words:

<i>beard</i>	<i>age</i>
<i>fierce</i>	<i>bike</i>
<i>grouse</i>	<i>bone</i>
<i>home</i>	<i>brow</i>
<i>house</i>	<i>crain</i>
<i>load</i>	<i>fine</i>
<i>loud</i>	<i>kite</i>
<i>paper</i>	<i>pine</i>
<i>scarce</i>	<i>shade</i>
<i>taste</i>	<i>sure</i>
<i>void</i>	<i>voice</i>

English vowels can be lengthened depending on their position. In particular, vowels in open syllables are pronounced longer. In a closed syllable, vowels are pronounced briefly. Voiced consonants contribute to the lengthening of vowels, while vowels combined with voiceless consonants are shortened in pronunciation. In modern English, there is a large database for defining pronunciation standards and recording changes in them. The database of examples is made up of large language corpora. An obvious example of literary pronunciation is audio recordings of artistic and other types of publications. English vocalism consists of 11 monophthongs – /i:/, /ʊ/, /e/, /æ/,

² Hickey R. A Dictionary of Varieties of English. Malden, MA: Wiley-Blackwell. – 2010; Hickey R. Legacies of Colonial English. Studies in Transported Dialects. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. – 2004.

/h/, /š:/, /s/, /s:/, /G/, /u:/, / t:/ and 8 diphthongs - eʊ/, /aʊ/, /ɛʊ/, /əG/, /aG/, /ʊə/, /Gə /, /eə/. These elements are studied in closed and open joints under the following connection conditions:

Voiced consonant + vowel + voiced consonant;

Voiced consonant + vowel + unvoiced consonant;

Voiced consonant + vowel + voiced consonant;

Unstressed consonant + vowel + unstressed consonant;

Unvoiced consonant + vowel + voiced consonant;

Voiceless consonant + vowel + voiced consonant;

Sonorous consonant + vowel + sonorous consonant;

Sonorous consonant + vowel + voiced consonant;

Sonorous consonant + vowel + voiceless consonant;

Vowel + consonant;

Vowel + voiceless consonant;

Vowel + sonorous consonant;

Verbal consonant + vowel

Voiceless consonant + vowel

Sonor consonant + vowel

In English, as above, localization in cooperation with stress has a direct effect on vowel length.

At the beginning of the last century, Uzbek linguistics began to focus on the issues of the place of formation, composition, combination properties and classification of sounds based on various signs. Physiological, acoustic and linguistic properties of Uzbek sounds were studied according to the principles of traditional linguistics. As the first two points are related to the investigation of human natural capabilities, it is known that the linguistic feature becomes a matter of pure linguistics as it means the influence of sound on the meaning of words³. Moreover, the linguist scientist L. Shcherba gives priority to the linguistic feature in phoneme classification. Physiological and acoustic indicators can concentrate on several sounds. However, the ability to distinguish meaning and affect meaning is considered a unique parameter for each sound⁴. After the general description of the sound system was formed, A. Abduazizov introduced a completely new approach to Uzbek phonetics. Underlying his views is the dialectical principle. The study of sounds from the point of view of generality-specificity, in turn, serves as a theoretical basis for the phonetic paradigm.

Traditional Uzbek phonetics provides three different classification options for the vowel system:

1. Classification according to the place of appearance;
2. Classification according to mouth and tongue activity;
3. Classification according to lip involvement.

Uzbek vocalism does not have complex symbols like diphthongs and triphthongs typical of Western languages. So, monophthongs are divided into wide vowels a, (ã), o, õ and narrow vowels i, ï, ü, u.

³ Bondarko L., Verbitskaya L., Gordina M. Fundamentals of general phonetics;

⁴ Nurmonov A. Phonology and morphology of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1992; Abduazizov A. Phonology and morphology of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1992;

Vowels in the upper part of the tongue: i, i, y, u, o'.

Vowels in the middle rise of the tongue: e, ö, ö, o.

Low rise vowels: ə, ö, o, ə⁵.

While citing these classifications, it should be noted that they are general and conditional. Because in speech conditions, these indicators change due to a person's articulation capabilities and dialect peculiarities. According to the presence of the lip, Uzbek vowels are divided into unlabbed a, ä, i, i and labeled o, ö, u, y types. Only this classification does not lose its relevance in speech conditions. As you can see, the Western school of phonetics emphasizes the acoustic classification of vowels. This is due to the presence of complex sound units such as diphthongs and triphthongs in these languages. In the Uzbek language, vocalism consists of monophthongs, therefore, classifications are made based on articulatory indicators of sound formation.

From a paradigmatic point of view, vowels enter into conflicting relations according to their length. Both long and short versions of one vowel exist in all Turkic languages: i - girl, bir, six, mix; i - book, nature, money / u - three, puch, power; u - grape, autumn, system. / e - land, sweat, give; e - earth; early The sign of nasality in the production of vowels means the participation of the nasal tympanic membrane. This sign is not observed in the norms of Uzbek literary pronunciation.

The presence of the lips in the pronunciation of vowels, the place of formation, the functions of the tongue and the palate are paradigmatic signs common to the Uzbek literary language and dialects. For this reason, these factors take place in the center of the field of vocalism. Vowels are noted as a characteristic of some dialects, which is not determined by the standards of literary pronunciation. For example, the back and front row vowels are also based on the difference between Qarluq and Kipchak dialects. In the Oghuz dialect, the degree of vowel length is an important parameter that distinguishes meaning. It follows that in dialectal vocalism, it is peripheral indicators such as length and nasality that become the main object of research. In the Uzbek language, the position of the vowel does not affect the length of the pronunciation in some places. For example, in open syllables, vowels are not pronounced longer than in English, in words with closed syllables and open syllables, vowels are pronounced with the same length: tulip, sky, body, night, say, shame, mysterious, free, man, tribute - officially, partially, honest, hole, conscience.

When talking about short and long vowels, it should be noted that there were 8 vowel sounds in ancient vocalism: a, y, o, u, ə, i, ö, ü. In the modern Uzbek literary language, long and short i sounds have been generalized and included in the list of y consonants. Also, synharmonism, which historically exists in the Uzbek language, i.e., the mutual adaptation of sounds in a word as a result of fusion, is not observed in the current standard of literary pronunciation. Synharmonism is preserved in the dialects, but it is not recognized as a literary language standard due to the complexity of the spelling system. So, in vocalism, we can add dialectal synharmony to the list of research objects along with length, line and nasality parameters.

If we consider phonetics as a paradigm, it is necessary to consider the influence of other language levels on it. For example, the lexicon of the ancient Turkic language has acquired the appearance of having no borrowed lexemes. Over the centuries, the integration of Persian and Arabic influenced the lexical composition of the language, and this influence was also reflected in phonetics. Elements such as polysyllabic words, series of consonants, and obtuse characters appeared, which were not observed in the Turkish language. It is also necessary to emphasize the negative impact of historical and political processes on the Turkish language. As a result of political pressure and neglect, the alphabet of the Turkic languages was not fully formed. Orhun Enasay and Sogdian writings were practically not preserved even in the case of synthesis. First, we turned to Arabic graphics, then to

⁵ Mirtojiev M. Phonetics of the Uzbek language. Tashkent: Science, 1991. -B.20.

Cyrillic and Latin graphics - the opportunity to return to our first script was completely missed during a huge historical period. The phonetic and lexical content, as well as the grammatical structure, changes as language development is conditioned by internal and external factors.

Problems in the study of vocalism can be divided into two. The first group of issues has always existed and has not lost its relevance today:

1. Record pronunciation changes in the vowel system;
2. Describe the characteristics of vowels in dialects;
3. Determining the interaction between vowels and consonants.

The second group of tasks arose in accordance with the new requirements:

1. Vowel spelling programming for artificial intelligence;
2. Coordination of dialectal features in vowel pronunciation with literary language;
3. Determining the impact of acquisition and international lexical level on the vocalism system is gaining relevance.

Carrying out the listed tasks in a comparative aspect gives a number of practical results. In particular, a theoretical basis will be created for assimilating the latest phonetic modifications in foreign language education, expanding the capabilities of artificial intelligence through the phonetic level - that is, improving the recording of speech in written form, and regularly updating transcription forms in bilingual dictionaries. It is known that pronunciation examples are not reflected in Uzbek electronic dictionaries. Also, there is no electronic, large-scale form of dialectal dictionaries in English and Uzbek languages. Research on dialectal characteristics of vocalism will be a theoretical resource to fill this gap.

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